

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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PROMOTION OF URINARY CONTINENCE: NURSE DRIVEN EVIDENCE-BASED
GUIDELINE FOR URINARY INCONTINENCE AMONG STROKE SURVIVORS

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

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ABSTRACT

Urinary incontinence among stroke survivors in inpatient rehabilitation facilities is a significant healthcare challenge. Despite efforts by nurses to treat and manage urinary incontinence (UI) among stroke survivors, it remains a troublesome post-stroke sequela. One possible reason is that nurses may not be addressing the specific UI needs of the stroke survivor. The purpose of this quality improvement project was to improve continence among stroke survivors by developing and implementing an evidence-based guideline. The Integrated Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services framework was used to guide implementation and evaluation of the project. The Promotion of Urinary Continence (PUC) guideline was developed using accredited guidelines and expert opinion on the promotion of urinary continence. The PUC guideline was implemented following education to unit nursing staff and information to other key stakeholders (physicians, administrators, other clinicians). Patients with functional independence measures bladder scores (FIMBS) of ≤ 4 upon admission were compared before and after PUC guideline implementation. Each patient's FIMBS change was calculated comparing admission and discharge score change. The results indicated a 31% increase in the post-PUC patients' mean scores of FIMBS when compared with pre-PUC patients' mean FIMBS. The post-PUC mean FIMBS was significantly increased from the pre-PUC mean FIMBS, $t(2.32) = 81, p = .023$. Therefore, the PUC guideline interventions resulted in 31% increase in the continence rate among stroke survivors over the three-month period of the project. The project also created awareness of the

prevalence and incidence of UI among stroke survivors and appropriate measures to manage it. Biannual staff in-service education and integration of the PUC guideline into online charting will lead to sustainability of the project's benefit to stroke survivor function.

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INTRODUCTION

Stroke is a devastating disease, which affects both patients and their family members. With stroke or cerebrovascular accident (CVA), a part or section of the brain is denied oxygenated blood (Robinson, Odle, Frey, & Hodgkins, 2013) due to an ischemic or hemorrhagic incident, which may lead to partial or permanent disability and in some cases even death (Muir, 2013). The disabilities experienced by stroke survivors include paralysis or hemiparesis of extremities, dysphagia, memory deficits, speech and language impairments, and urinary incontinence. Urinary incontinence (UI) as it relates to neurogenic bladder (NB) is experienced by 60% of stroke survivors (Chou, Jiang, Harnod, & Kuo, 2013).

Background to the Problem

The rate of UI is increasing despite inpatient rehabilitation efforts to treat and manage it (Hubbard et al., 2012). One possible reason is that nurses may not be adequately addressing the needs of the stroke survivor as it relates to UI (Jordan et al., 2011). This may be related to gaps in documentation, treatment, knowledge, or training among nursing staff (Jordan et al., 2011). Given their ongoing interactions with patients and their providers, nurses are in the prime position to address this problem and should address UIs using all available resources, such as professional organization guidelines, and collaboration with other interdisciplinary team members.

Despite the acknowledgement of the prevalence of UI among the post stroke patients by healthcare professionals, most rehabilitation units do not have specific guidelines for managing this problem (Hubbard et al., 2012). The 46-bed stroke unit of a rehabilitation hospital in Southern California provides services to patients aged over 18

years, who have stroke and neuromuscular disorders. Stroke patients comprise more than 90% of these patients. On this stroke unit, no evidence-based guideline (EBG) or policy to target UI exists. Due to the unavailability of such a guideline, implementation and documentation of recommended care strategies for UI are inconsistent and there is a need for a new approach to this problem.

Significance of the Problem

Post stroke voiding dysfunction has serious implications for patients. Urinary incontinence may lead to bladder infections, sepsis, disruption of required therapies, increase in hospitalized days, and failure to discharge to home (Jordan et al., 2011; Pilcher & MacArthur, 2012; Watkins et al., 2012). Given the negative effects of UI, intervening early during hospitalization may minimize complications and co-morbidities. Urinary incontinence and urinary retention (UR) are interchangeable as they relate to neurogenic bladder in post stroke survivors. As such, stroke-related neurogenic bladder leads to urinary leakage and retention of urine (Pilcher & MacArthur, 2012), which are treatable conditions (Chou, Jiang, Harnod, & Kuo, 2013).

Statement of Purpose

With proper UI treatment, stroke survivors can be restored to a functional state, which allows easy transition back to the home setting. The goal is to allow stroke survivors to live a meaningful life, which is not hindered by UI (Jordan et al., 2011; Pilcher & MacArthur, 2012). Therefore, the purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project will be to improve continence among stroke survivors suffering from UI by developing and implementing an EBG, educating and empowering nursing staff to

address the gaps in the management and treatment of UI on a 46-bed stroke unit in a rehabilitation hospital in Southern California.

Pathophysiology of Urinary Incontinence Post Stroke

Urinary incontinence has many causes and affects many people. Understanding the pathophysiology of UI among post stroke patients helps in assessment, identification, management and treatment, as well as in the evaluation of interventions. There are various perspectives as related to the cause or origination of UI aftermath of CVA. Neuronal control of urination is complex and involves pathways across the brain and including the spinal cord and peripheral nerves. Multiple neurotransmitters are necessary for urination to occur normally. With stroke where an infarction or cerebral edema hinders the main neurologic pathway for voiding, UI can result (Dumoulin, Korner-Bitensky, & Tannenbaum, 2005). Several motor areas control the bladder, sphincter, and the pelvic floor: frontal cortex, cingulate cortex, basal ganglia, hypothalamus, and cerebellum (Pizzi et al., 2014); damage to any of these areas by stroke can lead to UI. Beyond disruption of neuro-micturition pathways, other factors contribute to UI post stroke (Cournan et al., 2012): cognitive and language deficit, motor impairment, and medication use.

According to International Continence Society (ICS), three UI types are recognized: stress, urgency, and mixed UI (Dumoulin et al., 2005). Fisher (2014) further differentiates these, stating that post stroke patients experience stress, urge, overflow, functional, mixed, and/or transient UI.

Table 1

Definitions, Causes, and Guidelines for Urinary Incontinence (UI)

Types and Definition of UI	Pathophysiology	Treatment
Urge UI (UII) (Destructor over activity). Abrupt urgency and frequency. Inability of bladder to store urine.	Neuromicturition pathways destruction due to stroke	History & physical assessment, timed voiding (Cognitively sound) or prompted voiding (Cognitively impaired), bladder retraining, anticholinergic medication
Stress Incontinence (SUI) Leakage of small amount of urine due to activities such as coughing, sneezing, walking stair, lifting or bending	Stroke is not the root cause but can aggravate it.	Lifestyle change, physical assessment, timed voiding, PFMT, medication
Mixed UI (SUI & UII) Leakage of urine having features of both stress and urge	UII is related to stroke but SUI might be pre-existing condition	Treat the most bothering issue first
Functional UI Urine loss because of challenges to use the restroom or devices.	Stroke impact on physical, cognitive and communication abilities (impairments)	Timed or prompted voiding.
Transient UI Urinary accident or loss as a result of factors such as medication, infection, constipation or delirium	Medication side effects, urinary tract infection, bowel obstruction or impaction, vaginitis and delirium, which are reversible conditions.	Underlying causes assess and treat promptly.
Overflow Incontinence (Destructor Hyporeflexia) Bladder distention due to excessive urine retention	Loss of bladder tone and factors that are not stroke related. This leads to incomplete bladder emptying.	Timed voiding (double voiding), intermittent catheter, bowel program, medication
Impaired Awareness Inability to sense the fullness of bladder before leakage.	Massive destruction or impairment of neurological pathway for voiding	Behavioral therapies.

Adapted from “Schematic diagram representing the causes and types of post-stroke urinary incontinence,” by Mehdi, Z., Birns, J., & Bhalla, A. (2013). Post-stroke urinary incontinence. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*, 67(11), 1128-1137. doi:10.1111/ijcp.12183.

General and specific interventions for UI are recommended from different organizations’ guidelines (Bettez et al., 2012; Burkhard et al., 2016; Vaughn, 2009).

Some key interventions from these guidelines include:

- Use of behavioral therapies (timed or prompted, toileting assistance and bladder training, double voiding and Crede's maneuver)
- Evaluation of bladder filling with bladder scanner,
- Information on urge inhibition,
- Avoid caffeinated drinks (bladder irritants)
- Urodynamic testing,
- Medications,
- Encouraging regular bowel movements,
- Increasing fluid intake, as appropriate,
- Thorough and daily assessment of UI history and symptoms,
- Pelvic floor muscle exercises,
- Discontinuation of indwelling catheter if not contraindicated,
- Intermittent catheterization (IC),
- Urinalysis, and Culture and Sensitivity if indicated,
- Use of urinals, bedpans, and containment pads.

Supporting Framework

The Integrated Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (iPARIHS) framework will be used to guide the QI project. As depicted in Figure 1, the iPARIHS framework has included areas that had been identified as missing in the previous PARIHS framework (Harvey & Kitson, 2015; Kitson & Harvey, 2016). Therefore, use of the iPARIHS framework aims to improve knowledge translation to practice (Harvey & Kitson, 2016) and can give a vivid explanation of knowledge into a meaningful practice change. This QI project will utilize the iPARIHS framework for implementation and evaluation by considering the appropriate constructs and their

subsets. The four key elements or constructs of the iPARIHS are innovation, recipients, context, and facilitation (Harvey & Kitson, 2016; Mudge et al., 2017). Within each construct are components that must be considered for successful implementation of the practice change (Harvey & Kitson, 2016).

Innovation

In the framework, consideration of the innovation or target change requires analysis of the knowledge about the innovation. Its basis in research evidence, clinical experiences in the area, and how the features of the innovation allow for easy transmission of knowledge about the innovation to change in practice (Mudge et al., 2017). The innovation comprises not only research or knowledge but also the extent of the applicability and relative advantage of research information.

Urinary incontinence guidelines will be gathered from select research institutions, databases, and clinical journals; appropriate evidence-based UI strategies will be compiled, which fit the rehabilitation setting. These will then be shared with staff through teaching strategies and recommendations for proper documentation.

Recipients

In the iPARIHS framework, recipients are the individuals and the collective team who will ensure successful implantation of the innovation into a change of practice (Kitson & Harvey, 2016). For this project, recipients are nurses, rehabilitation associates, stroke patients, doctors, therapist, and family members of the patients. The vitality of all persons involved in the practice change must be properly managed through facilitation (Mudge et al., 2017).

Context

Context encompasses not only the setting where the QI project will be initiated, but also factors that could have significant influence on the setting (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). Context is divided into inner and outer components. The inner context for this project is the stroke unit in a rehabilitation hospital in Southern California. The outer context includes the rehabilitation facility as a whole, which is considering a Magnet journey, as well as external bodies such as the Commission on Accreditation of Rehabilitation Facilities (CARF), The Joint Commission, and Association of Rehabilitation Nurses (ARN). The facilitation of factors within the inner and out context must be considered for successful implementation of the innovation.

Facilitation

The iPARIHS framework's uniqueness is the fourth construct, which is facilitation (Kitson & Harvey, 2016). As shown in Figure 1, facilitation includes the role of the facilitator in ensuring that knowledge translation occurs in order to have a change in practice (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). That is for a successful implementation of a plan, facilitation is the key to unlocking the potential of the other constructs.

Facilitator Focus and Activity

What the Facilitator Looks at

What the Facilitator Does

Source: Harvey G & Kitson A (2015) Implementing Evidence-Based Practice in Healthcare: A facilitation guide. Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge

Figure 1. The Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services integrated framework (i-PARIHS framework): Facilitation as the active ingredient (reprinted with permission from Kitson & Harvey, 2016).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A literature review was conducted to determine the available research regarding the topic of UI post stroke among adults 18 and over. The search focused on published EBGs containing recommendations for stroke-related UI, perceptions of patients and providers as they relate to UI, as well as education materials used to promote adoption of EBGs.

PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane, and PsycINFO databases were searched for relevant peer-reviewed articles on UI among post stroke survivors. The search terms included post stroke, cerebrovascular accident, urinary incontinence, urinary retention, urinary dysfunction, nursing adherence to guideline, UI guidelines, UI protocols, and change of behavior. Peer reviewed articles from 2012 to present were selected as well as one article from 2005, which provided a historical perspective of the topic of UI. Three search phrases were used to obtain relevant research articles from PubMed, CINAHL, and Cochrane as shown in Table 2.

Table 2

Search for evidence on UI interventions

Terms	Limitations	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
UI (UR, dysfunction) AND guidelines(protocols, best practices, management, OR treatment) AND post stroke (CVA)	Peer Reviewed, English, Date: 2012 – 2017. Except one article 2005	89	52	27	10

Note. Articles excluded were based on title, settings, duplication and contributions to project topic. CVA = cerebrovascular accident, UI = Urinary incontinence, UR = urinary retention.

A search for articles related to provider and patient perceptions and education of UI utilizing two phrases using the PubMed, CINAHL, Cochrane, and PsycINFO databases. Databases were searched using specific terms in order to optimize the search for relevant articles related to the QI project. Table 3 displays the combination of terms and the search outcomes. A total of 14 articles were gathered which were used to develop the literature review.

Table 3

Search for Evidence on Adherence and Education

Terms	Limitations	Articles Retrieved	Articles Excluded	Articles Reviewed	Articles Used
Education intervention AND change nurses behavior (professional adherence)	Peer Reviewed, English, Date: 2012 – 2017.	96	84	12	6

Note. Articles excluded were based on title, settings, duplication and contributions to project topic.

Urinary Incontinence

In the 21st century, the inclusion of EBGs or EBPs in nursing have been found to have enormous benefits as related to UI post stroke (Hubbard et al., 2012). Dumoulin, Korner-Bitensky, and Tannenbaum (2005) established the importance of EBGs in inpatient rehabilitation facilities (IRF) as related to UI. Despite the evolution of EBGs on UI post CVA in IRF, many IRFs lack protocols or EBGs pertaining to UI among post stroke patients (Dumoulin et al., 2005; Thomas et al., 2014). The demands for quality care, requires the need to engage in purposeful and cost-effective evidence-based

approaches to care for patients with UI post stroke. Compared to UK, Canada, and Australia, few intervention studies in the United States have been done to establish efficacy of using EBGs (Chesworth et al., 2015; Frasure, 2014; Thomas et al., 2015; Thomas et al., 2014).

The post stroke survivors in IRFs are there for restoration care in order to reach a functional level, which would allow patients to be discharged to home (Cournan, 2012). Dumoulin and colleagues (2005) found IRFs approach UI patients from two perspectives. The first perspective involves a compensatory approach, which encourages the patient to use their strengths to overcome the weaknesses they developed as a result of the stroke. The second perspective is the remedial approach, which involves helping the patient work on the areas of weakness that resulted from the stroke. Dumoulin and colleagues (2005) found the compensatory approach should be utilized when working with UI patients post stroke. This approach was more effective than the remedial approach. This would involve providing the UI patient access to the necessary support to allow them to obtain assistance for using the bedpan, urinal or restroom and avoid an accident in the bed (Pilcher & MacArthur, 2012).

Multiple studies have suggested treatment of UI patients is not about usual care but includes using evidence-based care in order to tailor treatment and decrease the incidence of UI (Cournan, 2012; Dumoulin et al., 2005; Fisher, 2014; Thomas et al., 2014). Each facility must develop its own approach to providing EBGs for treating UI patients post stroke. Providers are tasked with the responsibility of knowing how to implement the EBGs in the context of patient care (Fisher, 2014).

Behavioral Therapies and Medications

There is sufficient evidence to suggest treatment methods and medications are not a one size fits all formula when caring for UI patients. Because there are different types of UI, each requires its own systematic approach to treatment by providers (Fisher, 2014); thus, each type can be addressed differently using unique EBG bundles (Mehdi, Birns, & Bhalla, 2013). Timed and prompted voiding offers benefits for all UI post stroke patients. However, they must be used consistently in order to retrain the UI patient to regain continence. Dumoulin and colleagues (2005) found that timed voiding is appropriate for patients with no sensation and with episodes of UR. For this category of patients, post-void residual (PVR) measurement by use of bladder scan has also proven useful (Kim, Chun, Chang, & Yang, 2015). The prompted voiding method has been discovered to be a better option for patients who retained the sensation to urinate as well as had a UR episode (Cournan, 2012; Dumoulin et al., 2005; Thomas et al., 2014).

The limitation to most of the studies reviewed was the exclusion of aphasic patients in most behavioral therapies in managing UI or UR (Cournan, 2012; Dumoulin et al., 2005). This does not allow the provider to see the full scope of the effectiveness of the EBGs when treating all UI and UR patients. The risk of infection and trauma are reasons not to catheterize patients. However, intermittent catheterization may be the last step for unresolved UR (Kim et al., 2015). A study revealed that a combination of interventions decreased the need for catheterization by 6% (Thomas et al., 2015). Subsequently, there was more than 67% improvement in continence for urge incontinence patients with a combination of behavioral therapies (Thomas et al., 2014).

A combination of pelvic floor muscle exercises (PFME) and bladder re-training (BR) showed a 75% reduction in UI episodes by type of stroke and UI patients against 6.4% in control group (Dumoulin et al., 2005). In addition, in the same study, the combination of BR, urge suppression (US) and PFME was used successfully for men with urge UI (Dumoulin et al., 2005). While Cournan (2012) found the involvement of physical therapists (PT) made the PFME intervention more likely to be successful, some argue the use of PFME in management of stroke patients is problematic. For example, Thomas and colleagues (2014) found PFME was removed due to unwillingness of the PTs to assist in initiating this intervention.

Behavioral therapies and medications are helpful in promotion of continence (Chou et al., 2013; Thomas et al., 2015). Nurses are responsible for identifying the optimal combination of therapies to promote continence. That is, bundling interventions for UI with an emphasis on individualized preferences led to a 67% improvement in continence (Fisher, 2014; Mehdi et al., 2013). Bundling can be based upon UI type or individual patient characteristics (e.g., mobility and functional status). Fisher (2014) noted for those suffering with UR, if patients have bowel regularity and good fluid intake, they have improved outcomes when using prompted voiding. Briefly, every salient point and potential obstacles will be considered in this QI project. There is a need to consider expert opinions concerning some of the interventions due to the lack of recent studies, most specifically in the area of medications.

Perceptions and Education

The relevance of EBGs cannot be ignored; however, knowledgeable staff is required in order to apply them into practice (Brady et al., 2016). Brady and colleagues

(2016) evaluated nurses' knowledge regarding EBGs when treating UI patients. Nurse knowledge was limited with regards to UI and integration of EBGs into practice, most especially in differentiating UI types and pathophysiology of UI. However, upon receiving education on both EBGs and UI disease process, there was a 53% increase in the ability of nurses to distinguish UI types (Mathis, Ehlman, Dugger, Harrawood, & Kraft, 2013). Therefore, nurses were able to identify and use interventions, which targeted specific patient needs (Brady et al., 2016; Cournan, 2012; Fisher, 2014).

Frasure (2014) demonstrated the use of educational strategies for staff when treating patients with UI brought about positive perceptions by nurses and improved quality of care. According to Brady and colleagues (2016), staff training (educational resources-/in-services) assisted nurses in acknowledging patient perceptions of their UI. Lack of awareness led to poor coordination of care by nurses who did not utilize EBG when treating patients (Brady et al., 2016). The focus of this paper is not about the educational strategies for promotion of the EBG. However, this will be discussed briefly. Frasure (2014) revealed that appropriate educational activities and evaluation were effective in creating practice change, which resulted to better patient experience. Therefore, such tools for successful implementation of the EBG will guide this project.

Moreover, continuation of education is a necessary component for implementing EBGs in assessing/treating UI. Such education assists with maintaining fidelity of the implementation of EBG by nurses (Chesworth et al., 2015; Cournan, 2012). According to Frasure (2014), educational interventions resulted in a 50% increase in the rate of adoption of EBG. The level of education a nurse obtains enhances the rates of adoption and fidelity to EBG (Frasure, 2014). That is, nurses with higher education have less

resistance to EBPs or EBGs. In addition, mentors and project change agents must have a strong foundation in the utilization of EBG. This will promote better assimilation of frontline nurses into participating in the implementation of best practices for improved continence (Frasure, 2014).

The types of educational approaches also influenced documentation appropriateness and perceptions of nurses (Chesworth et al., 2015). Brady and colleagues (2016) reiterated continence care should be sufficiently flexible in order to accommodate the latest research and empower staff to promote continence among post stroke survivors. Mehdi and colleagues (2013) evaluated provider perceptions during the process of adopting EBG using Functional Independence Measures (FIM) and usual care when treating UI patients. They indicated that FIM use increased the promotion of continence above the usual care. In addition, Fisher and colleagues (2014) demonstrated the role of perceptions when implementing EBGs in the promotion of continence. Optimal teaching strategies combined with good educational materials (posters, algorithm, and pocket cards) are important for promoting EBG (Brady et al., 2016; Mathis et al., 2013). The combination of classroom, online, posters and pocket cards have been proven to be effective in promoting EGB (Brady et al., 2016; Mathis et al., 2013)

Furthermore, despite the time EBG implementation might seem to take, nurses reported that timed and prompted voiding were less time consuming when compared with cleaning after incontinent patients (Cournan, 2012). Patient preference must be considered in choice of care strategies, as shown by reports of patients preferring use of bedside commodes over bed pans (Pilcher & MacArthur, 2012). It could be deduced that the element of gravity might help in emptying the bladder by using objects that allow

partial or full out of bed privileges if not contraindicated. The educational intervention must be dynamic enough to consider the task or responsibility of the providers in content and context. That is, the content of licensed (registered nurses and licensed vocational nurses) must be different from unlicensed (nurse assistants). In addition, there is a need for continued education in order to maintain adherence to the innovation and sustainability.

METHODS

Design

This QI project utilized published EBGs in developing a urinary incontinence (UI) specific guideline along with staff education, and materials for post-stroke survivors in a stroke unit of IRF in Southern California. Guided by the Integrated Promoting Action on Research Implementation in Health Services (iPARIHS) framework, the promotion of urinary continence (PUC) guideline was implemented using multifaceted strategies. Therefore, the purpose of this QI project is to improve the outcomes of UI among stroke survivors by addressing the gaps in management and treatment.

This is the first UI specific guideline for stroke survivors to be put into action at the project facility. In line with the iPARIHS framework, the 'innovation' is the PUC guideline. This innovation was developed according to the unique features of the hospital. According to Harvey and Kitson (2016), innovation must be produced by "tinkering," which involved tailoring EBGs in line with recipient and content needs by the facilitator. However, most of the evidence-based measures described in the literature review are currently in place but are not systematically implemented across all patients. To begin the project, the facilitator solicited ideas and strategies from the unit manager and the unit educator to fine-tune the innovation (PUC). The primary facilitator of this project is a DNP student (author). The author included all the various elements of the iPARIHS framework in developing, teaching, promoting and implementing the PUC guideline.

The facilitator developed educational materials and organized classes for disseminating the PUC guideline to the nursing staff. The facilitator roles and the facilitation process work to promote successful implementation and results (Harvey &

Kitson, 2016). The facilitator of this QI project involved all stakeholders (recipients, inner and outer contexts) to ensure all aspects (PUC guideline, education and implementation) were covered for successful implementation of the QI project in order to lead to a sustainable practice change. The iPARIHS framework as depicted in Figure 1, displays the cycling nature revealing projection from the facilitation to other constructs for a successful project implementation (Harvey & Kitson, 2015).

Innovation

The PUC is the innovation, which has been developed for the change of practice concerning management of UI among stroke survivors. The PUC guideline (Appendix C) was prepared using various accredited guidelines and expert opinions in IRF for stroke survivors suffering from UI. The clinical guidelines for stroke management from American, Australian, Canadian, European, and United Kingdom Stroke Associations coupled with research studies (Langhorne, Bernhardt, & Kwakkel, 2011; Mangnall, 2012; Thüroff et al., 2011; Wilson, 2016; Wissel, Olver, & Sunnerhagen, 2013) were employed.

The unique feature of the PUC guideline was based on a three-step approach to managing UI at the request of the current facility. The initial tools were double voiding, modified pelvic floor muscle exercises and the three-step process, which are timed/prompted voiding, habit training, and bladder training. This demonstrated the facility capacity and stakeholders' requests were highly considered per iPARIHS. The PUC guideline consists of background, assessment, recipients, medical history, goals, overview of UI, management, expected outcomes, and a sample bladder program form. The innovation was designed in a style that was easy to understand and implement.

Ethical Considerations

Prior to implementing this QI project, approval was sought from Rancho Research Institute Institutional Review Board (IRB) and CSUF IRB. The project was found to be free of harm to recipients. Therefore, exception letters were issued from both institutions for this project. The letters are attached in the Appendix A and Appendix B for reference.

Recipients

The QI project recipients were nursing staff and stroke patients. The direct recipients were the nursing staff, and indirect recipients were the stroke survivors. This project was designed for a change of practice of the nursing staff (recipients). The nursing staff included Registered Nurses (RNs), Licensed Vocational Nurses (LVNs), Rehabilitation Associates (RAs) and Nursing Attendants (NAs) of which were educated regarding the PUC guideline and implementation process.

The author with the approval of the unit manager and unit educator developed the education bundle. The education bundle included the complete PUC guideline, a two-page summary of PUC, and a PowerPoint that informed and prepared recipients for a successful practice change. The author consulted with a leading researcher in Australia who had implemented similar QI projects (Jordan et al., 2011). The Australian author's scholarly feedback and materials supported the work of this project.

The education class was 30 minutes in duration with more than 15 educational sessions taught in groups or individual classes. The facilitator taught the class, which educated the recipients of practice change regarding EBGs for evaluation, management, and treatment of UI among stroke survivors. The topics included the prevalence of UI in

stroke survivors, UI types and symptoms, a three-step approach for bladder management, functional independence measure (FIM) and documentation (see appendix E).

Fifty-seven recipients (28 RNs, 2 RN Supervisors, 1 Unit Manger, 1 Nursing Administrator, 4 LVNs, 4 RAs, 12 NAs, and 5 Nursing students) participated in the 30-minute educational classes. Despite it being a mandatory class, only 90% of the recipients (RNs, LVNs, RAs, NAs) of the project's unit were educated on the PUC. The physicians and other interdisciplinary team members (therapists, social workers, and case managers) were informed of the QI project. The medical providers (physicians and physician assistants) were given the PUC guideline and encouraged to order a bladder scan, and post void residual (PVR) for all stroke survivors admitted to the unit.

The indirect recipients were the stroke survivors. For evaluation of this project, the impact of the practice change for stroke survivors was examined. The review of pre and post PUC implementation samples consisted of stroke survivors with FIM bladder scores (FIMBS) of less than or equal to four (≤ 4) upon admission. A retrospective chart review using the electronic medical record (EMR) was conducted to extract stroke survivors with less than or equal to 4 FIMBS upon admission in the last three months before the educational interventions for the recipients was implemented.

The post data was collected for three months following staff education on PUC guideline. The sample included both males and females. Patients were ethnically diverse as the facility admits patients who are Hispanic, African American, Caucasian, and Asian-American. The pre and post PUC sample sizes consisted of 84 and 82 stroke survivors respectively. One of the exclusion criteria used was the length of stay (LOS) of six days. Any patient with a LOS of less than six days was excluded from both samples.

The EBG interventions used to manage and treat UI take several days to implement and see improvements in urinary continence (Cournan, 2012; French et al., 2016; Hubbard et al., 2012; Mehdi, Birns, & Bhalla, 2013; Thomas et al., 2014). Therefore, for this project it would require at least six days to determine the effect of the PUC guideline implementation on a stroke survivor's health. This is in light of the average 14 days of LOS in inpatient rehabilitation facility.

Inner Context

The project setting is a hospital located in Southern California, which has been serving Los Angeles County for over a century. The hospital is licensed for 289 beds and serves as a rehabilitation center for patients with a mixture of medical conditions. The patients receive a variety of medical-surgical services and rehabilitation services. The rehabilitation services include stroke, spinal cord injury, brain injury, pediatrics, orthopedics, diabetes care, pressure ulcer management, limb preservation, and post-amputation care. The hospital provides care to approximately 4,000 inpatients and 71,000 outpatients annually, making it one of the largest rehabilitation centers in the nation. The QI project was implemented in the 46-bed stroke unit of the facility. The unit manager and educator were integral parts in the planning and execution of the QI project. The collaborative support of the facility's stakeholders came from the chief nursing officer, nursing administrator, rehabilitation FIM specialist, education department, and advanced practice committee.

Outer Context

The iPARIHS framework emphasizes the importance of the outer context for successful implementation of change in practice (Harvey & Kitson, 2016). The facility is

concomitantly seeking Magnet status, and this project was part of a nurse-driven quality improvement and evidence-based practice effort. The PUC guideline, educational material, and implementation were completed and aligned with the CARF, the Joint Commission, and ARN recommendations. The QI project's facility is a publicly owned IRF, and the project was conducted according to the regulations governing the establishment.

Data Collection and Measures

Changes in bladder control data were collected based upon the patient's Functional Independence Measure Bladder Score (FIMBS). A FIMBS™ score was collected within 72 hours following admission to the rehabilitation unit, and within 72 hours prior to being discharged. The FIMBS was completed to determine bladder function. A change score was obtained by averaging the admission FIMBS from the discharge FIMBS during the pre and post-intervention period. The FIMBS ranges from 1 to 7, with 1 (Total Assistance) being the lowest possible score and 7 (Complete Independence) being the best possible score. The goal of using FIMBS was to determine the level of bladder management needed. Bladder management was the level at which the patient can open the urinary sphincter without incontinence occurring and having conscious control.

The facility has access to the nationally recognized rehabilitation database (eRehabData) as mandated by CMS (Cournan, 2012). The FIM has become a reliable tool used for more than two decades in capturing changes in post-stroke and other neuromuscular disorders or accidents within IRFs (Cournan, 2012). Therefore, FIM was a validated tool utilized in the rehabilitation setting, most specifically among stroke

survivors (Cournan, 2012; Meyer et al., 2015). The advantage of using the FIM instrument over the Barthel Index was the inclusion of the burden of care, which included information, which was sensitive and comprehensive regarding patient care needs (Meyer et al., 2015). The total sum of FIM scores ranged from 18 to 126, and higher scores indicated greater functional independence.

The FIMBSs percentage change was conducted in comparing the means of the convenience sample per the set criteria and the patients who participated in the intervention. The FIM includes various sections; however, the most relevant section for this project included the bladder management section. The bladder management section is divided into two parts: Bladder level of assistance and bladder frequency of accidents.

The post monthly FIMBS means change was performed in this project to determine the pattern of change in the innovation (PUC) implementation (using Run Chart). The post three-month intervention FIMBSs was compared using increases or decreases in percentage to check the significance of the change for each month. The data was collected and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) and Windows 10 Excel.

The author identified the pre-data according to the criteria beginning July 1, 2017 through September 30, 2017. The facility Rehabilitation FIM specialist had validated the data before it was retrieved. The data was double-checked by the author in differentiating stroke survivors from other neurological patients FIMBSs. The unit also cared for neurological patients including Guillain-Barre syndrome, multiple sclerosis, amyotrophic lateral sclerosis, and brain tumor resection. However, more than 90% of the patients were stroke patients. For pre-intervention data, 84 stroke survivors met the inclusion criteria as

outlined: LOS at least six days, FIMBS score upon admission ≤ 4 . The data was retrieved from the EMR following discharge.

The educational activities of the PUC guideline were implemented beginning October 2, 2017 through October 8, 2017. Two sessions were conducted on October 11 and 12, 2017 for staff that missed the initial scheduled classes. The PUC guideline implementation began on October 9, 2017. The bladder program training form (See Appendix C) was placed on the bathroom door of every stroke survivor admitted with FIMBS scores of ≤ 4 . The author began the initiation of the bladder program and updated this form. The bladder program training's form was developed to inform and remind staff as well as for monitoring the progress of the PUC implementation. The bladder program training form did not replace the mandatory online charting in the EMR of each patient. The post PUC implementation data from October 14, 2017 through January 14, 2018 was collected from the EMR per stipulated criteria. The data retrieved from the EMR for pre and post PUC was coded and de-identified using Windows 10 Excel by the author. The data could not be traced to individual patients.

The primary aim of this QI project was to promote continence among stroke survivors by implementing an EBP guideline. The impact of the guideline implementation was evaluated using FIMBSs. The mean scores, standard deviation, and percentage were calculated using Excel and SPSS for pre and post data. The results used for the mean score was taken by subtracting the FIMBS upon admission (FIMBS A) from FIMBS at discharge (FIMBS D) and dividing it by the total sample number.

Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS version 24.0, which consisted of running a descriptive analysis, bivariate correlation and *t*-tests to describe sample features and PUC implementation outcomes. A *p*-value of <0.05 was used to establish statistical significance. Subsequently, Windows 10 Excel was used to determine the monthly data change for the post PUC by using a run chart. The pre and post implementation FIMBSs upon admission and FIMBSs at discharge were computed to determine the change in the FIMBS mean. The pre and post implementation FIMBS means were compared to indicate the clinical significance of PUC in the improvement of continence and increase in FIM. The pattern of gains and losses were calculated for each FIMBS group. The paired samples *t*-tests evaluated whether statistical significance of pre and post implementation FIMBS upon admission and FIMBS at discharge was achieved. The bivariate correlations (Pearson and Spearman's correlation) test were conducted to verify if other variables (i.e. LOS, Age, gender, stroke types, and aphasic) contributed to the percentage change in FIMBS means.

Results

The purpose of this QI project was to improve continence among stroke survivors in IRF via developing and implementing a PUC guideline. In addition, the nurses were educated regarding use of the PUC guideline for a successful implementation and outcome. The improvement in continence after PUC implementation was measured using an increase in FIMBS mean percentage when compared to pre and post implementation FIMBS means.

Table 4 contains the data for the pre-patient sample size ($N = 84$), ischemic (50; 59.5%), Hemorrhagic (34; 40.5%), pre-implementation gender (male 51; 60.7%, female 33; 39.3%), pre-mean age (56 years), and pre-mean LOS (15 days). The age ranged from a minimum of 34 years to a maximum of 80 years. The LOS ranged from 6 days to 26 days. Another feature was the communicative ability of the pre-sample; non-aphasic (68; 81.0%) and aphasic (16; 19.0%).

Table 4

Demographic of Pre PUC Stroke Survivors

Demographic	<i>M (SD)</i>	Frequency <i>N = 84</i>	Percentage %	Min	Max
Patient's Stroke Type					
Ischemic		50	59.5		
Hemorrhagic		34	40.5		
Patient's Gender					
Male		51	60.7		
Female		33	39.3		
Patient's Communication					
Non-Aphasic		68	81		
Aphasic		16	19		
Patient's Age					
	55.63 (10.8)			34	80
18-39		7	8.3		
40-59		44	52.4		
60-79		32	38.1		
80+		1	1.2		
Patient's LOS					
	15.15(4.69)			6	26
6-14		41	48.8		
15-23		39	46.4		
24+		4	4.8		

Table 5 shows data regarding the post PUC patient sample size ($N = 82$); ischemic, (60; 73.2%) and hemorrhagic (22; 26.8%), post PUC gender (male 60; 73.2%; female 22; 26.8%), post PUC mean age (56 years), and post PUC mean LOS (16 days). The age ranged from a minimum of 34 years to a maximum of 82 years. The LOS ranged from 6 days to 33 days with a mean of 15.54 days. Table 5 also includes data for the communicative ability of the post sample, non-aphasic (69; 84.1%) and aphasic (13; 18.9%).

Figure 2. The pre implementation FIMBSs gains and losses from admission to discharge.

Table 5

Demographic of Post PUC Stroke Survivors

Demographic	<i>M (SD)</i>	Frequency	Percentage	Min	Max
		<i>N</i> = 82	%		
Patient's Stroke Type					
Ischemic		60	73.2		
Hemorrhagic		22	26.8		
Patient's Gender					
Male		60	73.2		
Female		22	26.8		
Patient's Communication					
Non-Aphasic		69	84.1		
Aphasic		13	18.9		
Patient's Age					
	56.16 (9.55)			34	82
18-39		6	7.3		
40-59		46	56.1		
60-79		28	34.1		
80+		2	2.4		
Patient's LOS					
	15.54 (5.83)			6	33
6-14		34	42.0		
15-23		43	53.1		
24+		4	4.9		

Figure 3. The post implementation FIMBSs gains and losses from admission to discharge.

Figure 2 and Figure 3 show the change in the FIMBS gains and losses. In comparison of the data highlighted in Figures 2 and 3, the pattern of gains and losses are depicted for pre and post implementation. At value 0, the results were 35.7% and 20.7%, pre and post implementation respectively. Thus, there was no change in the FIMBS at discharge from admission. The results showed for both values -2 and -1, less than 5% of the samples experienced a decrease in FIMBS in pre and post implementation. If there was a reduction in FIMBS D, as in the example of a patient admitted with FIMBS of 4 and discharge score were 3, this was indicative of a loss. The values -2 and -1 in Figures 2 and 3 indicated there was a loss in FIMBS at discharge. The values 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 in

Figures 4 and 5 showed there was a gain in FIMBS D when compared with FIMBS A. The gains were demonstrated by an increase from FIMBS A to FIMBS D. For example, a patient admitted with FIMBS of 3 and at discharge the FIMBS was 4 constitutes a gain. For an increase of 1 (Figures 2 & 3), results indicated that 14 (16.7%) and 18 (22%) gains pre and post implementation respectively. At gain 2, 15 (17.9%) and 19 (23.2%), pre and post PUC respectively. For the increase of 3, pre was 13 (15.5%), and the post was 9 (11.0%). At 4, the pre was 7 (8.3%) and the post was 12 (14.6%). The last gain was 5, pre was 1 (1.2%), and the post was 3 (3.7%).

Table 6

Summary of Descriptive Statistics for Pre and Post Implementation FIMBSs

Items	<i>N</i>	<i>M (SD)</i>
Pre FIMBS Admit (FIMBS A)	84	2.20 (1.17)
Pre FIMBS Discharge (FIMBS D)	84	3.51 (1.88)
Pre FIMBS Result (FIMBS D - FIMBS A)	84	1.31 (1.53)
Post PUC FIMBS Admit	82	1.96 (1.15)
Post PUC FIMBS Discharge	82	3.68 (1.67)
Post PUC FIMBS Result	82	1.72 (1.60)

Pre and post evaluation of FIMBS demonstrated a mean change in scores of 1.31 and 1.72 as shown in Table 6. Therefore, this resulted in 31% increase in the post-PUC mean scores of FIMBS when compared with pre-mean FIMBS scores. These findings are indicative that PUC guideline implementation brought about a clinical change in FIMBS mean and most especially improvement in the continence rate of participants. In testing the hypothesis that the pre and post PUC FIMBS means were statistically significantly different, a one-sample *t*-test was performed. The assumption was the average FIMBS

gain was 1.31 (pre-FIMBS mean change), which was used as the basis for the post-FIMBS mean. The one sample t -test revealed the post FIMBS mean was statistically significant, $t(2.32) = 81, p = .023$ when compared with pre FIMBS mean.

Table 7

Summary of Pearson Correlations Tests for Post FIMBS Mean and Other Variables (N = 82)

Variables	r	p
Post PUC LOS	-.02	.85
Post PUC Age	-.06	.59
Post PUC Stroke type	-.05	.66
Post PUC Aphasic	-.07	.53
Post PUC Gender	-.08	.45

The Pearson correlation tests were conducted to verify whether other variables (i.e. LOS, Age, gender, stroke types, and aphasia) contributed to the percentage change in post implementation FIMBS mean. In Table 7, there was no statistically significant correlation between the FIMBS change and LOS ($r = -0.2, p = .85$) for the study population $N = 82$. In addition, there was no statistically significant correlation between the FIMBS change and other variables tested.

Table 8

Summary of Spearman's Correlations Tests for Post FIMBS Mean and other Variables (N = 82)

Variables	r_s	p
Post PUC LOS	-.10	.37
Post PUC Age	-.11	.34
Post PUC Stroke type	-.05	.63
Post PUC Aphasic	-.08	.48
Post PUC Gender	-.09	.42

The series of Spearman's correlation tests conducted failed in detecting any statistically significant relationship between the change in FIMBS mean and the other variables (Table 8). For instance in Table 8, the post PUC gender has a negative correlation with change in FIMBS mean and it was not statistically significant ($r_s(81) = -.09, p = 0.42$). Therefore, PUC bundle was the only variable that had a statistically significant effect in the increase of FIMBS.

Figure 4. Post monthly FIMBS means change.

The run chart highlights the monthly increase in post PUC FIMBS means, which indicated consistency in implementation. There was a steady increase in the gain of FIMBS means on a monthly basis. In addition, this increase was indicative that staff used the guidelines as directed and were adherent to the PUC guideline and its implementation.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this quality improvement (QI) project was to address the gap in the management of urinary incontinence (UI) among stroke survivors through the development, implementation, and evaluation of the PUC guideline through education and empowerment of the nursing staff to bring about change in practice and increase in Functional Independence Measure Bladder Score (FIMBS). This QI project developed a unit specific evidence-based guideline in promoting continence among stroke survivors in IRF. The essence of EBP is to improve the quality of care being rendered by nurses (French et al., 2017; Wallis, 2012). The outcomes of this QI project suggested that significant results have occurred during the course of the three-month implementation. These contributions included access to PUC guideline, increase in nursing staff knowledge and awareness in managing UI among stroke survivors, and improvement in FIMBS. There was a change in the practice of managing UI among stroke survivors and a 31% increase in FIMBS mean change. In addition, there was a steady increase in the FIMBS each month of implementation.

The mean LOS for pre PUC was 15 days, while post PUC was 16 days. The post-PUC mean LOS was higher than the pre PUC mean LOS by one day. Therefore, the Pearson correlation tests were conducted for both pre PUC and post-PUC using FIMBS means, which showed there was no correlation between the FIMBS mean and LOS. This indicated a day difference between pre PUC and post-PUC has no substantial contribution to the increase in FIMBS means post-PUC.

The PUC guideline development and implementation was guided by the iPARIHS framework, which showed the relevance of tailoring an EBG at the QI project facility.

The effect of this QI project brought about a 31% increase in FIMBS mean post-implementation when compared to pre-FIMBS mean change. The PUC guideline would not have brought about practice change had there been limited education to the nursing staff and limited materials before and during implementation. Every clinical instruction or EBG must be accomplished with innovative educational interventions for a positive change in practice for UI management post stroke (Brady et al., 2016; Mathis et al., 2013). This calls for more educational programming in the sustainability of any QI project, which aims to change practice. The QI project was nurse-driven, and the focus was on the behavioral interventions as stated in the literature, which was available to the nurses to utilize in the promotion of urinary continence among stroke survivors in the IRF setting. The author attributed the successful implementation outcomes to the stakeholders' buy-in, committed nursing staff, and stroke survivors in understanding the benefits of the PUC guideline. The result of this QI project contributed to the readiness of the QI project facility to pursue Magnet status.

No other factors showed positive clinical contributions to the increase in FIMBS in post PUC implementation. The pre and post PUC implementation demographics (LOS, Age, Stroke types, and aphasic) did not have a statistically significant difference in the result achieved. Therefore, it can be concluded the main factor contributing to the improvement in FIMBS, urinary continence and practice change was the PUC bundle (guideline, education, and materials). In reviewing the data, a one-sample *t*-test indicated post PUC FIMBS mean difference was statistically significant.

The benefits of this QI project for stroke survivors had many intrinsic values to nursing staff and the facility. One of the benefits was increased awareness of the EBG in

nursing and its implication on practice change to the nursing staff and management. It promoted movement from traditional nursing to EBP changes to improve care. The PUC guideline emphasized nursing staff clinical judgment and the promotion of patient-centered care.

Limitations

There were limitations, which affected this QI project related to implementation and outcomes. One limitation included the issue of float nursing staff to the unit where the QI project was being implemented. These float nurses were not aware or adequately educated about the QI project. Float nurses often experience anxiety and are not fully aware of the specific needs of the unit (Bates, 2013). A second limitation included charting on the hard copy being placed on the patients' bathroom doors. In this unit, nursing staff was mandated to use computer-based charting. Thus, they were not charting on the hard copy. In reviewing paper and computer charting for this project, only 45% of the hard copy charting of bladder program was completed compared to the mandatory online charting, which was approximately 90%.

Recommendations

When an evidence-based guideline (EBG) is instituted, ongoing education has been found to be important in supporting continued change (Cournan, 2012). The EBG must be flexible enough to accommodate the changing needs of the healthcare industry. It is recommended a biannual in-service on the PUC guideline be implemented for sustainability of this QI project in the management of UI among stroke survivors in IRF.

The placement of the bladder training form on the patient restroom door was a reminder for the staff to monitor the progress achieved by an individual stroke survivor.

Frasure's (2014) study showed a reminder is important in the implementation of an EBG for nursing staff. That is, the form enabled nurses to see the patient's progress in their bladder-training program, which may have not been shared during the inter-shift report. In addition, computer-driven charting is now the norm. Therefore, the form is being proposed to be integrated into the online charting system, which will then prompt staff to use the correct measure per the guideline. This will make charting easier for the nursing staff. With this change, nursing staff will no longer need to place the bladder form on the patient's restroom door.

The QI project facility should incorporate a double voiding measure coupled with the initial three-step approach to promote urinary continence. Double voiding has been found to be effective in the promotion of urinary continence (Hoag & Gani, 2015). However, further studies are needed to address the modified pelvic floor muscle exercises used to manage UI in nurse-driven interventions.

Conclusion

The relevance of EBG or EBP in nursing cannot be denied; all nursing schools and healthcare facilities must increase awareness of the benefits to quality of care. The contributions of this QI project created awareness of the prevalence and incidence of UI among stroke survivors. It led to changes in practice and increased FIMBS at the implementation's facility. The iPARIHS framework guided this QI project, which facilitated collaborative efforts from stakeholders in the successful implementation and positive outcomes. Following the implementation, the focus was on developing individualized patient home care packages for continence (IPHPC). The essence of IPHPC is the average length of stay in IRF is 14 days and the measures to promote

continence might not be effective due to the limited time factor. The IPHPC will continue the work towards promotion of continence among stroke survivors following discharge. This QI project demonstrated the implementation of EBG in an IRF is both viable and practical in managing UI and improving continence among stroke survivors.

REFERENCES

- Bates, K. J. (2013). Floating as a reality: Helping nursing staff keep their heads above water. *MEDSURG Nursing*, 22(3), 197-199.
- Bettez, M., Le Mai Tu, K. C., Corcos, J., Gajewski, J., Jolivet, M., & Bailly, G. (2012). 2012 update: Guidelines for adult urinary incontinence collaborative consensus document for the Canadian Urological Association. *Canadian Urological Association Journal*, 6(5), 354.
- Brady, M. C., Jamieson, K., Bugge, C., Hagen, S., McClurg, D., Chalmers, C., & Langhorne, P. (2016). Caring for continence in stroke care settings: A qualitative study of patients' and staff perspectives on the implementation of a new continence care intervention. *Clinical rehabilitation*, 30(5), 481-494.
- Burkhard, F., Lucas, M., Berghmans, L., Bosch, J., Cruz, F., Lemack, G., . . . Tubaro, A. (2016). EAU guidelines on urinary incontinence. *Arnhem, The Netherlands: European Association of Urology*.
- Chesworth, B. M., Leathley, M. J., Thomas, L. H., Sutton, C. J., Forshaw, D., & Watkins, C. L. (2015). Assessing fidelity to treatment delivery in the ICONS (identifying continence options after stroke) cluster randomised feasibility trial. *BMC Medical Research Methodology*, 15(1), 68. doi:10.1186/s12874-015-0051-9
- Chou, Y.-C., Jiang, Y.-H., Harnod, T., & Kuo, H.-C. (2013). Characteristics of neurogenic voiding dysfunction in cerebellar stroke: A cross-sectional, retrospective video urodynamic study. *The Cerebellum*, 12(5), 601-606. doi:10.1007/s12311-013-0468-9

- Cournan, M. (2012). Bladder management in female stroke survivors: Translating research into practice. *Rehabilitation Nursing, 37*(5), 220-230.
- Dumoulin, C., Korner-Bitensky, N., & Tannenbaum, C. (2005). Urinary incontinence after stroke: does rehabilitation make a difference? A systematic review of the effectiveness of behavioral therapy. *Topics in stroke rehabilitation, 12*(3), 66-76.
- Fisher, A. R. (2014). Development of clinical practice guidelines for urinary continence care of adult stroke survivors in acute and rehabilitation settings. *Canadian Journal of Neuroscience Nursing, 36*(3), 16-31.
- Frasure, J. S. (2014). The effectiveness of four translation strategies on nurses' adoption of an evidence-based bladder protocol. *Journal of Neuroscience Nursing, 46*(4), 218-226.
- French, B., Thomas, L. H., Harrison, J., Coupe, J., Roe, B., Booth, J., . . . Carer, G. (2017). Client and clinical staff perceptions of barriers to and enablers of the uptake and delivery of behavioural interventions for urinary incontinence: Qualitative evidence synthesis. *Journal of Advanced Nursing, 73*(1), 21-38.
doi:10.1111/jan.13083
- Harvey, G., & Kitson, A. (2015). *Implementing evidence-based practice in healthcare: A facilitation guide*: Routledge.
- Harvey, G., & Kitson, A. (2016). PARIHS revisited: From heuristic to integrated framework for the successful implementation of knowledge into practice. *Implementation Science, 11*(1), 33. doi:10.1186/s13012-016-0398-2

- Hoag, N., & Gani, J. (2015). Underactive bladder: Clinical features, urodynamic parameters, and treatment. *International Neurourology Journal*, *19*(3), 185-189. doi:10.5213/inj.2015.19.3.185
- Hubbard, I. J., Harris, D., Kilkenny, M. F., Faux, S. G., Pollack, M. R., & Cadilhac, D. A. (2012). Adherence to clinical guidelines improves patient outcomes in Australian audit of stroke rehabilitation practice. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, *93*(6), 965-971. doi:http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.apmr.2012.01.011
- Jordan, L.-A., Quain, D., Marsden, D., White, J., Bullen, K., Wright, S., . . . Baines, H. (2011). Managing urinary continence following stroke: Can we do better? *HNE Handover: For Nurses and Midwives*, *4*(1).
- Kim, T. G., Chun, M. H., Chang, M. C., & Yang, S. (2015). Outcomes of drug-resistant urinary retention in patients in the early stage of stroke. *Annals of rehabilitation medicine*, *39*(2), 262-267. doi:10.5535/arm.2015.39.2.262
- Kitson, A. L., & Harvey, G. (2016). Methods to succeed in effective knowledge translation in clinical practice. *Journal of Nursing Scholarship*, *48*(3), 294-302. doi:10.1111/jnu.12206
- Langhorne, P., Bernhardt, J., & Kwakkel, G. (2011). Stroke rehabilitation. *The Lancet*, *377*(9778), 1693-1702.
- Mangnall, J. (2012). Promoting patient safety in continence care. *Nursing Standard*, *26*(23), 49-56.

- Mathis, S., Ehlman, K., Dugger, B. R., Harrawood, A., & Kraft, C. M. (2013). Bladder buzz: The effect of a 6-week evidence-based staff education program on knowledge and attitudes regarding urinary incontinence in a nursing home. *The Journal of Continuing Education in Nursing*.
- Mehdi, Z., Birns, J., & Bhalla, A. (2013). Post-stroke urinary incontinence. *International Journal of Clinical Practice*, 67(11), 1128-1137. doi:10.1111/ijcp.12183
- Meyer, M. J., Pereira, S., McClure, A., Teasell, R., Thind, A., Koval, J., . . . Speechley, M. (2015). A systematic review of studies reporting multivariable models to predict functional outcomes after post-stroke inpatient rehabilitation. *Disabil Rehabil*, 37(15), 1316-1323. doi:10.3109/09638288.2014.963706
- Mudge, A. M., Banks, M. D., Barnett, A. G., Blackberry, I., Graves, N., Green, T., . . . Kurrle, S. (2017). CHERISH (collaboration for hospitalised elders reducing the impact of stays in hospital): Protocol for a multi-site improvement program to reduce geriatric syndromes in older inpatients. *BMC geriatrics*, 17(1), 11.
- Muir, K. W. (2013). Stroke. *Medicine*, 41(3), 169-174.
doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.mpmed.2012.12.005>
- Pilcher, M., & MacArthur, J. (2012). Patient experiences of bladder problems following stroke. *Nursing Standard*, 26(36), 39-46.
- Pizzi, A., Falsini, C., Martini, M., Rossetti, M. A., Verdesca, S., & Tosto, A. (2014). Urinary incontinence after ischemic stroke: Clinical and urodynamic studies. *Neurourology and Urodynamics*, 33(4), 420-425. doi:10.1002/nau.22420

- Robinson, R., Odle, T. G., Frey, R. J., & Hodgkins, F. (2013). Stroke. In B. Narins (Ed.), *The Gale Encyclopedia of Nursing and Allied Health* (3rd ed. ed., Vol. 5, pp. 3222-3228). Detroit: Gale.
- Thomas, L. H., French, B., Sutton, C. J., Forshaw, D., Leathley, M. J., Burton, C. R., . . . McColl, E. (2015). Identifying continence options after stroke (ICONS): An evidence synthesis, case study and exploratory cluster randomised controlled trial of the introduction of a systematic voiding programme for patients with urinary incontinence after stroke in secondary care. *Programme Grants for Applied Research*, 3(1).
- Thomas, L. H., Watkins, C. L., Sutton, C. J., Forshaw, D., Leathley, M. J., French, B., . . . Britt, D. (2014). Identifying continence options after stroke (ICONS): a cluster randomised controlled feasibility trial. *Trials*, 15(1), 509.
- Thüroff, J. W., Abrams, P., Andersson, K.-E., Artibani, W., Chapple, C. R., Drake, M. J., . . . Tubaro, A. (2011). EAU guidelines on urinary incontinence. *Actas Urológicas Españolas (English Edition)*, 35(7), 373-388.
- Vaughn, S. (2009). Efficacy of urinary guidelines in the management of post-stroke incontinence. *International Journal of Urological Nursing*, 3(1), 4-12.
- Wallis, L. (2012). Barriers to implementing evidence-based practice remain high for US nurses. *AJN The American Journal of Nursing*, 112(12), 15.
- Watkins, C. L., Leathley, M. J., Chalmers, C., Curley, C., Fitzgerald, J. E., Reid, L., & Williams, J. (2012). Promoting stroke-specific education. *Nursing Standard*, 26(39), 35-40.

Wilson, J. A. (2016). The Management of urinary incontinence. *US Pharm*, 41(9), 22-26.

Wissel, J., Olver, J., & Sunnerhagen, K. S. (2013). Navigating the poststroke continuum of care. *Journal of Stroke and Cerebrovascular Diseases*, 22(1), 1-8.

doi:<http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.jstrokecerebrovasdis.2011.05.021>

APPENDIX A
RANCHO IRB APPROVAL

July 21, 2017

Abayomi Lawal, R.N.
Doctoral Candidate, Nursing Practice Program
California State University, Fullerton

Dear Mr. Lawal,

Thank you for presenting your Doctoral Project Proposal, "Promotion of Continence among Stroke Survivors", to our Institutional Review Board (IRB) for consideration.

After reviewing your study with the IRB Administrator, we feel it does not fit the requirements of research. Since your quality improvement project focuses on developing and implementing guidelines and/or policy on urinary incontinence to educate and empower the inpatient nursing staff at Rancho Los Amigos National Rehabilitation Center, it does not meet the qualifications of a 'systematic investigation, designed to develop or contribute to generalizable knowledge'.

The IRB would like to acknowledge your quality improvement proposal and ask that you forward them a copy of the outcome when you have completed your project.

Best wishes on your upcoming Doctorate. Please let me know if I can assist you further.

Regards,

Yago Szlachcic, M.D.
Chair, Institutional Review Board
Rancho Research Institute, Inc.
Chair, Department of Medicine
Rancho Los Amigos National Rehabilitation Center

YS:bm

APPENDIX B
CSUF IRB APPROVAL

CALIFORNIA STATE UNIVERSITY, FULLERTON

Dear Abayomi Lawal,

Re: **Promotion of Urinary Continence Among Stroke Survivors**

The above mentioned protocol submission has been reviewed and approved. The IRB Approval notice and consent form (if applicable) will be sent via campus mail to your Faculty Advisor, Dr. Deanna Jung, in the School of Nursing.

If you have any questions, please feel free to contact our office at irb@fullerton.edu.

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APPENDIX C

PROMOTION OF URINARY CONTINENCE AMONG STROKE SURVIVORS

Guideline for Urinary Incontinence

This guideline is designed to assist nurses and affiliated nursing staff in assessing, managing, and treating urinary incontinence (UI) among stroke survivors in an inpatient rehabilitation setting by providing an analytical framework. This guideline is not meant to replace staff clinical judgment.

Background

UI is an unwanted urine leakage or retention. Neuronal control of urination is complex and involves pathways across the brain, including the spinal cord and peripheral nerves. UI can result, when a stroke caused by an infarction or results in cerebral edema that hinders the main neurologic pathway for voiding. At least 6 out of every ten stroke survivors suffers from UI.

Assessment

Every stroke survivor that is admitted should be assessed regarding the following items:

- History taking
- Physical examination
- Observation of leakage
- Measurement of residual volume
- Bladder charting
- Urinalysis (sign of foul smelling urine or patient c/o burning sensation or indwelling catheter in place)

Performed by: RNs, LVNs, NAs, RAs and affiliated Student Nurses under direct supervision of a licensed nurse. Patient initial assessment should be undertaken by an RN to determine the types of UI and the presence or absence of pre-existing conditions.

Medical History: Patient information will be gathered regarding; Benign prostatic hyperplasia (BPH), Prostatectomy, Constipation, Atrophic vaginitis/urethritis, Chronic Kidney disease, Diabetes mellitus, Congestive heart failure, Vaginal prolapse, Medications (Diuretics, Anticholinergic agents, Psychotropic, Narcotic analgesics).

Goals

1. Nurses and affiliated nursing staff will utilize this evidenced-based guideline for assessment and management of stroke survivors with UI.
2. Stroke survivors with UI will gain continence or in progress of gaining continence and not have UI associated complications.

Definitions, Causes, and Guidelines for UI

Types and Definition of UI	Pathophysiology	Treatment
Urge UI (UII) (Destructor over activity), Abrupt urgency and frequency. Inability of bladder to store urine	Neuromicturition pathways destroyed due to stroke	History & physical assessment, timed voiding (Cognitively sound) or prompted voiding (Cognitively impaired), bladder retraining, anticholinergic medication
Stress Incontinence (SUI) Leakage of small amount of urine due to activities such as coughing, sneezing, walking stair, lifting or bending	Stroke is not the root cause but can aggravate it	Lifestyle change, physical assessment, timed voiding, PFMT, medication
Mixed UI (SUI & UII) Leakage of urine having features of both stress and urgency	UII is related to stroke but SUI may be a pre-existing condition	Treat the most bothersome issue first
Functional UI Urine loss because of challenges to use the restroom or devices	Stroke impact on physical, cognitive and communication abilities (impairments)	Timed or prompted voiding
Transient UI Urinary accident or loss as a result of such factors as	Medication side effects, urinary tract infection, bowel obstruction or impaction, vaginitis and	Underlying causes assess and treat promptly

medication, infection, constipation or delirium	delirium, which are reversible conditions.	
Overflow Incontinence (Destructor Hyporeflexia) Bladder distention due to excessive urine retention	Loss of bladder tone and factors that are not stroke related. This leads to incomplete bladder emptying.	Timed voiding (double voiding), intermittent catheter, bowel program, medication
Impaired Awareness Inability to sense the fullness of bladder before leakage	Massive destruction or impairment of neurological pathway for voiding	Behavioral therapies

Management

Behavioral techniques are listed below and will be used according to the UI types and the needs of the patients, which are those requiring passive involvement and those requiring active participation: Toileting interventions – urinal, bedpan, intermittent catheterization (IC), timed/scheduled toileting, prompted voiding, habit training, and bladder retraining.

1. Stress UI

- Timed /scheduled or prompted voiding
- PVR/ bladder scan every 4-6 hrs, if a patient has not voided or no desire to void.
- Bladder training

2. Urge/Urgency/Functional UI

- Timed /scheduled or prompted voiding
- PVR & bladder scan every 4-6 hrs, if a patient has not voided or no desire to void.
IC if PVR or bladder scan ≥ 300
- Habit training
- Bladder training

3. Urinary Retention/Impaired Awareness/Overflow UI

- Timed /scheduled or prompted voiding

- PVR & bladder scan every 4-6 hrs, if a patient has not voided or no desire to void.
IC if PVR or Bladder Scan \geq 300
- Medication is strongly encouraged
- Habit training
- Bladder training

FIM Documentation

- Input and Output documentation
- Toileting Locations: Bedpan, Urinal, Toilet, incontinent
- Accident or Spilt
- Level of Assistance
- Hard copy should be filled and transcribed to ORCHID
- By 30 minutes before end of every shift

Definition of Terms and Instructions

1. **Timed voiding** is voiding initiated by the patient, while 'prompted voiding' is voiding initiated by the nurses/staff.

What is Prompted Voiding?

- Toileting program that includes a toileting schedule, verbal feedback, and positive reinforcement
- Educate patient and family members of continence awareness

Which patients are best for this bladder program?

Cognitively impaired patients and aphasic patients who are:

- Able to say their name

- Able to follow instructions or
- Consistent with “Yes” or “No” answers
- Can reliably point to one or two objects

The Five Steps of Prompted Voiding:

- I. Check: Check patient clothing or linens on regular basis for wetness (inform patient what you are doing).
- II. Talk: Encourage patient to talk about bladder problem and wetness to increase awareness of condition.
- III. Prompt: Say, “Would you like to use the bathroom? I can help you to the bathroom now. Please give it a try.”
- IV. Praise: Praise for being dry or attempting to use toilet. Say, “Great, you tried to use the bathroom” or “It has been three hours, and you have remained dry—good job.”
- V. Correction: If patient is wet, indicate desire for dryness. Say, “You were wet this time; please call before you have to go next time.”

2. Habit Training

Toileting at set intervals to match patient’s typical voiding habits.

How:

Successful completion and documentation of voiding pattern for three days via timed/scheduled voiding or prompted voiding

- Keep and review bladder activities (documentation)
- Identify times patient is likely to void and schedule toileting at those times
- Usually every two to three hours after meals

- If no incontinence for 24 hours, can increase interval by 30–60 minutes.

3. Bladder Retraining

- Voiding on a schedule with progressively longer periods between voiding—
always with positive reinforcement
- Work with patient to resist the strong urge to void and wait for the next scheduled voiding
- Gradually extending the time between visits until your bladder learns how to ‘hold on’ at least for 20 minutes.

Why 20 minutes?

The goal of a 20 minutes voiding hold is based on the expectation that in the community, the patient should be reasonably able to reach bathroom facilities within 20 minutes and remain continent.

How?

- Take slow deep breaths to relax bladder.
- Which patients are best for this bladder program?
- Fairly independent in ADLs, occasional incontinence, aware of need to urinate

Expected Outcomes

1. Stroke survivors will have fewer or no episodes of UI and its associated complications
2. Stroke survivors will gain continence or in progress.
3. Nurses will intervene appropriately in managing and treating UI among stroke survivors
4. EBGs will be tailored to each patient’s needs

Sample Bladder Program Form

RANCHO LOS AMIGOS NATIONAL REHABILITATION CENTER
BLADDER TRAINING PROGRAM

WEEK: _____ ROOM: _____ BED: _____

TV-Q 2 hrs.							
HT-Q ___ hrs.							
BT-hold ___ sec./min.		BT-hold ___ sec./min.		BT-hold ___ sec./min.		BT-hold ___ sec./min.	
(M/D/Y) Day 1	(M/D/Y) Day 2	(M/D/Y) Day 3	(M/D/Y) Day 4	(M/D/Y) Day 5	(M/D/Y) Day 6	(M/D/Y) Day 7	(M/D/Y) Day 7
23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
24	24	24	24	24	24	24	24
01	01	01	01	01	01	01	01
02	02	02	02	02	02	02	02
03	03	03	03	03	03	03	03
04	04	04	04	04	04	04	04
05	05	05	05	05	05	05	05
06	06	06	06	06	06	06	06
07	07	07	07	07	07	07	07
08	08	08	08	08	08	08	08
09	09	09	09	09	09	09	09
10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
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16	16	16	16	16	16	16	16
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18	18	18	18	18	18	18	18
19	19	19	19	19	19	19	19
20	20	20	20	20	20	20	20
21	21	21	21	21	21	21	21
22	22	22	22	22	22	22	22
COMMENTS:	COMMENTS:	COMMENTS:	COMMENTS:	COMMENTS:	COMMENTS:	COMMENTS:	COMMENTS:

LEGEND: V=VOID I=INCONTINENT O=NO VOID

8/25/2017

Summary

General Nursing UI Interventions

1. Admission: History taking, Physical examination, Observation of leakage, Measurement of residual volume, Bladder charting, and urinalysis.
2. PVR for 48-72 hours
3. Identify and treat causes of transient UI
4. Maintain adequate fluid intake and hydration schedule
5. Limit dietary bladder irritants
6. Documentation of assessment and interventions appropriately
7. Prevent constipation episode
8. Interdisciplinary interventions

9. Intermittent Catheterization (IC)
10. Timed/or prompted voiding for 3 days
11. Habit training for 3 days
12. Bladder Training for 3 days: Day 1 for 5mins; Day 2 for 10 mins; & Day 3 for 20mins
13. Continence

APPENDIX D
SUMMARY OF PUC

Promotion of Urinary Continence among Stroke Survivors

Urinary Incontinence (UI) is unwanted urine leakage or retention. At least 6 out of every ten stroke survivors suffers from UI. Effects: Sepsis, UTI, therapies disruption, discharge problem, and psychosocial. Different types of UI: stress, urge, impaired awareness, overflow, functional, mixed, and/or transient.

Management

Behavioral techniques are listed below and will be used according to the UI types and the needs of the patients, which are those requiring passive involvement and those requiring active participation: Toileting interventions – urinal, bedpan, intermittent catheterization (IC), timed/scheduled toileting, prompted voiding, habit training, and bladder retraining.

Stress UI: Timed /scheduled or prompted voiding, PVR/ bladder scan every 4-6 hrs- if a patient has not voided or no desire to void, and bladder training.

Urge/Urgency/Functional UI: Timed /scheduled or prompted voiding, PVR/bladder scan every 4-6 hrs-if a patient has not voided or no desire to void, IC if PVR or bladder scan ≥ 300 , habit training, and bladder training.

Urinary Retention/Impaired Awareness/Overflow UI: Timed /scheduled or prompted voiding, PVR & bladder scan every 4-6 hrs, if a patient has not voided or no desire to void. IC if PVR or bladder Scan ≥ 300 , medication is strongly encouraged, habit training, and bladder training.

A 3-Step Approach for Bladder Retraining

1. Timed (Scheduled) voiding or prompted voiding: Timed voiding is voiding initiated by the patient, while ‘prompted voiding’ is voiding initiated by the nurses/staff.
2. Habit Training: Toileting at set intervals to match patient’s typical voiding habits
3. Bladder training: Voiding on a schedule with progressively longer periods between voiding—always with positive reinforcement. Gradually extending the time between visits until your bladder learns how to ‘hold on’ at least for 20 minutes.

Functional Independence Measure Bladder Scores (FIMBS) Documentation

1. Input and Output
2. Continent, incontinent or inconsistent
3. Toileting Locations: Bedpan, urinal, toilet, and IC.
4. Accident or Spilt
5. Level of Assistance
6. Hard copy should be filled and transcribed to ORCHID
7. By 30 minutes before end of every shift

Summary

1. Average length of stay is 14 days
2. Admission: History taking, physical examination, observation of leakage, measurement of residual volume, bladder charting, urinalysis, FIMBS at admission, daily and goal.

3. Inclusion criteria: stroke survivors with FIMBS ≤ 4
4. PVR for 48-72 hours and daily as ordered
5. Identify and treat causes of transient UI
6. Identify presence of UI and types of UI
7. Intermittent Catheterization (IC) as needed
8. Timed/or prompted voiding for 3 days
9. Habit training for 3 days
10. Bladder Training for 3 days: Day 1 for 5mins; Day 2 for 10 mins; & Day 3 for 20mins
11. Continence/in progress
12. Discharge FIMBS

APPENDIX E

PROMOTION OF URINARY CONTINENCE AMONG STROKE SURVIVORS LESSON PLAN

TRAINING GOAL: Ensure that training participants gain a thorough understanding of the need to promote urinary continence among stroke survivors. Understanding will begin from urinary incontinence (UI) to its implications, and strategies used for treatment in order to properly document.

Learning Objectives (2 minutes)

1. Discuss factors that need to be present to maintain urinary continence
2. Describe all the components for completing the physical assessment and medical history for UI patients
3. Identify risk factors for UI patients
4. Differentiate between UI types, and describe appropriate treatment options for each type
5. Describe the process for completing admission and daily UI charting and its impact on Functional Independence Measure Bladder Score (FIMBS).

Background (2 minute)

Urinary Incontinence is unwanted urine leakage or retention. Neuronal control of urination is complex and involves pathways across the brain, including the spinal cord and peripheral nerves. Urinary Incontinence can result, when a stroke caused by either an infarction or cerebral edema hinders the main neurologic pathway for voiding. At least 6 out of every ten stroke survivors suffers from UI.

Steps Needed to Urinate and Remain Continent (2 minutes)

The urinary system is a complicated process especially post stroke, and there are several steps that must be taken for a stroke survivor to be able to urinate without being incontinent. The patient must:

1. Have urine in the bladder: good kidney function. (This requires the kidneys to do their job by producing urine.).
2. Feel that the bladder needs to be emptied (This requires that the brain provide a signal to the person that it is time to void and the person be able to respond to the signal.).
3. Be able to wait until he or she gets to the bathroom (This requires brain and bladder muscle coordination to prevent the bladder from emptying too soon.).
4. Recognize the bathroom (This requires knowledge of the appropriate place to void).
5. Navigate to the bathroom alone or with help, and sit properly.
6. Undo clothing.
7. Send and receive a message from the brain to let the bladder sphincter muscle relax and let urine flow (This requires brain and bladder muscle coordination.)
8. Empty the bladder.

If there is a problem with any of these steps, incontinence can occur. Some of the problems can be easily treated; others need to be managed with appropriate interventions.

The most common causes of UI for stroke survivors are:

- Decreased functional ability
- Brain or nerve injuries from stroke
- Metabolic diseases such as diabetes

- Urinary tract problems, such as an enlarged prostate gland in men and pelvic muscle weakness in women.
- Urinary tract infections that can be treated.
- Medication side effects that can interfere with the ability to hold and release urine as well as controlling the volume of urine produced.
- Depression, which is usually treatable.
- Increased urine production caused by some illnesses. This condition may be controlled.
- Low fluid intake, which can be prevented.
- Fecal impaction (a severe form of constipation where a hard, dry stool is “stuck” in the large intestine). This can usually be prevented.
- Vaginal dryness from low estrogen levels in females. This condition can be treated.
- Length of time it takes for call light to be answered.
- Distance to the bathroom/commode.
- Lack of toileting programs.

Types and Symptoms of Urinary Incontinence (5 minutes)

1. Urge UI (UUI) (Destructor over activity): Abrupt urgency, frequency, and inability of bladder to store urine. Patient with UUI is unable to delay voiding after the sensation of bladder fullness is noted. Causative factor is stroke in most Stroke survivors.

2. Stress Incontinence (SUI): Leakage of small or large amount of urine due to activities such as coughing, sneezing, walking stair, lifting or bending. Stroke is not the root cause but can aggravate it.
3. Mixed UI (SUI & UUI): Leakage of urine having features of both stress and urgency.
4. Functional UI: Urine loss because of challenges to use the restroom or devices. Stroke impact on physical, cognitive and communication abilities (impairments).
5. Transient UI: Urinary accident or loss because of such factors as medication, infection, constipation or delirium. The factors that cause transient UI including medication side effects, urinary tract infection, bowel obstruction or impaction, vaginitis and delirium, which are reversible conditions.
6. Overflow Incontinence (Destructor Hyporeflexia): Bladder distention due to excessive urine retention. Patient with overflow UI experience a variety of symptoms such as frequent or constant dribbling, urge and stress incontinence, as well as urgent and frequent urination. They have frequent nighttime voiding, produce small amounts of urine with each voiding, and spend a long time on the toilet but produce only a weak, dribbling stream of urine. They often do not know they are leaking urine.
7. Impaired Awareness: Inability to sense the fullness of bladder before leakage.

A 3-Step Approach for Bladder Retraining (6 minutes)

The key to all bladder management methods is to determine the cause and amount of the incontinence. Sometimes the cause can be treated and the UI will improve or stop, as may be the case with transient UI.

1. Timed (Scheduled) voiding or prompted voiding: Timed voiding is voiding initiated by the patient, while ‘prompted voiding’ is voiding initiated by the nurses/staff.
2. Habit Training: Toileting at set intervals to match patient’s typical voiding habits
3. Bladder training: Voiding on a schedule with progressively longer periods between voiding—always with positive reinforcement. Gradually extending the time between visits until your bladder learns how to ‘hold on’ at least for 20 minutes

Why 20 minutes?

The goal of a 20 minutes voiding hold is based on the expectation that in the community, the patient should be reasonably able to reach bathroom facilities within 20 minutes and remain continent.

Functional Independence Measure (FIM™) (2 minutes)

The Functional Independence Measure (FIM™) instrument is a basic indicator of patient disability. The FIM™ is used to track the changes in the functional ability of a patient during an episode of hospital rehabilitative care. The FIM™ is comprised of 18 items, grouped into 2 subscales - motor and cognition. One of the 18 items is a Functional Independence Measure Bladder Scores (FIMBS) which UI guideline will target for improvement. A FIMBS™ score is collected within 72 hours after admission to the rehabilitation unit, and within 72 hours before discharge. The FIMBS will be used to

determine bladder function. The data related to FIMBS Scores of four and less (≤ 4) is the inclusion criterion, and from all available stroke survivors will be collected.

Documentation (3 minutes)

Nursing documentation is essential for good clinical communication. The accuracy of documentation is important. Appropriate documentation provides an accurate reflection of nursing assessments, changes in conditions, care provided and pertinent patient information which supports the multidisciplinary team in delivering optimal care.

Daily charting on patient's bladder management routine whether continent, incontinent, or accident and the level of assistance required (complete, modified independence, supervision/set up, minimum assist, maximum assist and complete) affects the FIMBS. The interventions needed to be documented include:

1. Admission: History taking, Physical examination, Observation of leakage, Measurement of residual volume, Bladder charting, and urinalysis, FIMBS at admission and goal.
2. PVR for 48-72 hours and daily as ordered
3. Identify and treat causes of transient UI
4. Maintain adequate fluid intake and hydration schedule
5. Continent, Incontinent, or inconsistent
6. Accident or spilt
7. Limit dietary bladder irritants
8. Assessment and interventions appropriately
9. Prevent constipation episode
10. Interdisciplinary interventions

11. Intermittent Catheterization (IC) as needed if no void
12. Timed/or prompted voiding for 3 days
13. Habit training for 3 days
14. Bladder Training for 3 days: Day 1 for 5mins; Day 2 for 10 mins; & Day 3 for 20mins
15. Continence/in progress
16. Discharge FIMBS

APPENDIX F
TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Table 1A

Evidence for Urinary Incontinence Interventions

Purpose	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To evaluate the evidence behind behavioral therapies for post stroke UI. (Dumoulin et al., 2005)	Systematic review	3 guidelines for UI 1 prospective Cohort study 4 RCTs	Effectiveness of 5 major therapies. Combination of the 2 or 3 therapies in treatment of UI. Remedial vs compensatory	Compensatory > remedial in approach to UI treatment. Timed Voiding based on expert opinions seems to be more useful for cognitive amb pts that having no sensation & episode of UR. PV appropriate for cognitive amb pts with sensation and UR episodes. Bladder retraining plus urge suppression useful for urges UI. BR + Urge Suppression + PFME for men with urge UI.	The usage of behavioral therapies improves continence. Validates differences in outcomes of UI interventions based upon UI types? Limitation: Limited to functional & amb post stroke pts. The outcomes of this study were based on consensus opinions.
To explore the significance of UI interventions in	Interventional study without randomization	Cases: nonrandomized 35	FIM used to measure relevance of	EBG implementation resulted in better FIM	IRFs should endeavor to embrace appropriate EBG

Purpose	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
restoration to continence of stroke survivors. (Cournan, 2012)	Key Variables: EBG (Enhanced bladder hx, timed & prompted voiding, bathroom training, & pelvic floor exercises), fidelity, re-education, EMR documentation.	female stroke survivors Controls: Discharged 35 female stroke survivors treated without the recent interventions IRF- Neurovascular unit, New York	interventions (Admission vs Discharge, Discharge – Admission = EBG) Fidelity evaluated using data from EMR by mean & SD	outcomes indicating improvement in continence level, 80% change in FIM score post intervention	for promotion of continence. Limitations: It is not solely nurse driven but interdisciplinary (nurses, OT & PT). It was time consuming The study was on non- aphasic females only. Nurses revealed that timed/prompted voiding was less time consuming than cleaning the outcome of incontinence
To indicate outcomes of initial feasibility of EBG application. (Thomas et al., 2014)	RCT 3 Arms (Usual care, Intervention care, & Supported Implementation) SVP (Bladder Training, pelvic muscle, or prompted voiding, & combination)	413 randomized participants (124 usual, 164 intervention, & 125 Supported). 12 (acute & rehabilitation Stroke unit) hospitals in England & Wales.	survey via questionnaires at 6 weeks & 12 weeks to measure continence status at discharge Odd Ratio (OR)>1 indicates effectiveness of interventions	Combinations of 2 arms of intervention indicated 1.50 times improvement in continence at discharge For urge incontinence, interventions arms had higher better outcomes of odd ratio greater than 1.66 In stress UI, supported arm had better result of continence at odd ratio of 1.82 & insignificant in other arms.	There were sufficient EBPs that bring about promotion of continence in IRF. Limitations: Mixed multitude of participants and facilities. Delay in recruitment.

Purpose	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To initiate & investigate SVP in treatment of UI among stroke survivors. (Thomas et al., 2015)	Evidence synthesis, case study and exploratory RCT. SVT(systematic voiding program)	Initiation: Articles on UI EBPs reviewed. Case Study (28 participants) Stroke unit in England.	% of articles that support SVP using CBI. # of continence after SVP # catheterization rate	The application of SVP via CBI improved continence. There was 21% improvement in continence as a result of SVP 6% decreased in catheterization rate	There was an improvement in continence when embracing EBG (SVP) in solving UI issue among post stroke survivor despite unfriendly organizational setting. Limitations: Small size for the case study.
To scrutinize and present EBG/intervention that enhances better management of UI post stroke. (Mehdi et al., 2013)	Systematic review. Assessment for UI. Interventions (behavioral, specialized input, complementary, & pharmacotherapy). Types of UI (DO & Urge, DH & overflow, & functional UI).	12 RCT articles & from 13 to 232 (724 participants). Hospitals and few communities.	Evaluation of appropriate interventions Effect of individualized bundle on UI	+ results but a larger trial needed. Bundle of interventions with individualized preference showed 67% improvement in continence	To have a good outcome of continence from these interventions, there must be appropriate assessment and individualized interventions. Limitations: Limited size data and evidence to definite agree on unique bundle.
To establish EBG for promotion of continence in post stroke survivors (Fisher, 2014)	Systematic review & Interventional study. CPG RNAO	21 articles reviewed & expert opinions for EBG for continence. 2 rehab facilities in Canada.	Assessed effectiveness of CPG	Chart audits revealed ↓ in UI. For UR, good bowel movement & fluid intake enhances prompted voiding. Dedicated staff, timely assessment & appropriate UI bundle promote continence.	There are reasons to implement EBG for UI among stroke survivors. Limitations: Small sample sizes.

Purpose	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To explore UI outcomes in pts with CVA and UR resistant to α -blocker and cholinergic. (Kim et al., 2015)	Retrospective study DV: UR, PVR IDV: CVA severity, sex, Aphasia, DM, functional ability, Kidney function. Cognitive function	33 CVA inpatients with drug-resistant UR (14 men & 19 women). Within 30 days after CVA onset. Rehabilitation hospital, Korea	UR is PVR \geq 100mL. Lesion location (supratentorial & infratentorial groups). K-MBI score is an overall reflection of CVA severity. UDS (areflexi & hyper-reflexic) Cognitive function was assessed using Korea Mini mental Status Examination	10 (30%) pts had PVR > 400 mL at discharge despite treatment. 70% of drug resistant pts did not recover from UI. 11(33%) of pts had resolved UR at discharge. 12 pts within the borderline of UR. \downarrow K-MBI score \uparrow CVA severity had? \uparrow UR risk with 67%. Higher functional status, walking ability, and non-aphasia related to better resolution of UR.	Since UR could not be eliminated in DRUR patients, clinicians should teach use of CIC for the 67% of patients who may not resolve. Limitations: small sample, retrospective study, & short follow up duration
To establish relationship in using EBG and patient outcomes. (Hubbard et al., 2012)	National audit data; correlational study Nurses using EBG, specifically AU Clinical Guidelines for Stroke Rehabilitation and Recovery. (Adherence) Discharge status; change in FIM score	68 Rehab units, Australia. Each contributed up to 40 stroke patients as cases. 2007-8	EBG Adherence = documentation of interventions per AU EBG. FIM Score range from 18 (worst) and 126 (Best). QO = FIM score > 22 points from initial FIM	2119 cases audited Adherence to various recommendations highly variable (from 13 to 96%; 79% for urge incontinence) \uparrow in adherence to EBG \uparrow more discharge than being institutionalized.	Inculcation of EBG in clinical practices commands QI. Limitations: retrospectively, Personalized care made it difficult to be adherence to EBG sometimes.

Purpose	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	from admission to discharge?		Discharge status	FIM score ≥ 100 = discharge home When urge incontinence EBG followed, pts more likely to go home ($p = .05$), and more likely to have \uparrow FIM scores ($p = .02$)	
To explore CVA pts' perspective on bladder problems in first 2 weeks after stroke. (Pilcher & MacArthur, 2012)	Descriptive qualitative study. Bladder problem, impact, therapeutic activities, satisfaction with bladder management. Effective communication	40 CVA pts IRF, Scotland. 9 focus group	2 phases: 25-item Questionnaire developed for pts. 3-item? Likert scale for urinary symptoms. Each term defined and appropriate terms were used for pts understanding. Impact = Concerns Focus groups with staff.	45% of the participants indicated concerns about their bladder problems. Reported problems: Erratic sleep pattern due to fear of UI, Prefer commode than bedpan. All parts of UI concerned pts, but especially when a linen change by staff was needed Urinary symptom frequency (2 weeks after stroke): urgency (65%), leakage of urine (57%), frequency (37%), nocturia (37%).	IDS should engage pts in therapeutic communication to alleviate fear of UI. Need for consideration Patient concerns in bladder management. Limitations: sample size is small. Questionnaires not well validated.

Purpose	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To investigate cerebellar stroke pts' voiding dysfunction via video urodynamic findings. (Chou et al., 2013)	Quantitative, retrospective, case-control study. DO, DU, VUDS, LUTD, USD, DUS, NUS, Ischemic, Hemorrhagic, Sphincter function, UI	Case: 15 pts with cerebellar stroke (8 ischemic & 7 hemorrhagic) Control: 31 they were not pts but were "healthy subjects" without LUTD. Hospital, Taiwan.	LUTD = LUTS = Voiding dysfunction. UN defined for men and women (Normal). UN = Qmax ≥ 15mL, PVR10% of CBC (CBC ≥ 350mL). DU has voiding efficiency ≤ 67% of the bladder capacity. DUS = ↑Pdet.Qmax	No difference in LUTS as regard to CVA locations and sizes. Pts were at different points post CVA. 75 % of pts with ischemic CVA had DO and DUS compared to 28.6 % of pts with hemorrhagic stroke. LUTD of cerebellar stroke patients likely also changes with time.	There is high incidence of DO & DUS 2+ months after cerebellar stroke. Effective and timely usage of VUDS very important in management of LUTD post cerebellar stroke Limitation: the small sample size

Note: # = number, % = percent, + = positive, > = greater than, ↑ = increase, ↓ = decrease, amb = ambulatory, AU = Australia, BR = bladder re-training, ĉ = with, CBC = Cystometric bladder capacity, CBI = combined behavioral interventions, CPG = clinical practice guideline, CVA = cerebrovascular accident, DM = diabetes mellitus, DO = Destrusor overactivity, DOIC = Destrusor overactivity with impaired contractivity, DRUR = drug-resistant urinary retention, DUS = Dyssynergic urethral sphincter, EBG = evidence-based guideline, EMR = electronic medical record, FIM care = interventional care, FIM = Functional Independence Measurement, hx = history, ICS = International Continence Society, IDS = interdisciplinary staff, IQoL = improved quality of life, IRF = inpatient-rehabilitation facility, K-MBI = Korean Modified Barthel Index, LUTD = Lower urinary tract dysfunction, LUTS = lower urinary tract symptoms, NA = nurse assistant, OR, odd ratio, OT = Occupational therapist, PFME = pelvic floor muscle exercise, popn = population, PT = Physical therapist, pts = patients, PV = prompted voiding, PVR = post voiding residual, QI = quality improvement, QO = quality outcomes, RCT = randomized controlled trial, RN = registered nurse, RNAO = Registered Nurses' Association of Ontario, SD = Standard deviation, SVP = systematic voiding program, UDS = urinary or bladder dysynergia sphincter, UI = Urinary incontinence, UN = Urodynamically normal, UR = urinary retention, US = urge suppression, vs = versus, VUDS = video urodynamic study.

Table 2a

Nurses Improvement, Patients' Preferences and Educational Resources

Purpose	Design, key variables	Sample, setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To evaluate professional needs in light of EBG in promoting Continence (Fisher, 2014)	Systematic reviews for EBG development; Pilot study using educational resources developed by group. Education resources. Barriers to CPGs. Knowledge, Attitude and Beliefs (KAB) of Nurses	EBG development – evaluation by panel of 25 local/regional experts: a) evaluating guidelines using the Appraisal of Guidelines Research and Evaluation (AGREE) Instrument ; and, b) focus groups to identify barriers/facilitators to implementation Pilot - 2 inpatient stroke units in Canada.	Evaluation of KAB & documentation post education. % of adherence Barriers to implementation	13% & 6.2% increase in knowledge & attitude respectively. A slight change in documentation noted. Educational interventions improved nurses' understanding and quality of care for UI in post stroke pts. Improved documentation Practice champions, Systemized educational program, & implementation of EBG on phases based.	The implementation of EBGs coupled with educational supports of nurses leads to quality care of UI post stroke survivors. Limitation: The shortage of personnel and resources. Pilot project sample size was small for generalization.
To explore impact of educational strategies on nurses in enhancing continence of stroke survivors. (Frasure, 2014)	Interventional study. Survey (pre & post) Pre = usual care & post = EBG & educational intervention Key Variables: 4 Strategies (educational materials,	20 nurses in stroke unit. USA	% of change in care. Adoption rate & nurse	When strategies adopted, continence outcomes improved by 21%. The rate of adoption of the intervention was 50% increased. Four strategies brought about better	IRF should endeavors to do embrace appropriate EBG for promotion of continence. results of tailored nurse-led EGB and supports far > than only EBG in UI actions.

	class, reminders ,& audit)			<p>perception and quality care than usual care (before the change).</p> <p>Better educated nurses have higher rate of adoption of EBG</p> <p>Supports (mentor & project change agent) promote better assimilation for frontline nurses that leads to better outcomes.</p>	<p>Limitations: The continuity of change was not accounted for.</p> <p>Single unit.</p>
<p>To explore significance of UI interventions in restoration to continence of stroke survivors.</p> <p>(Cournan, 2012)</p>	<p>Fidelity, re-education, EMR documentation.</p> <p>Fidelity (adherence, exposure, quality of delivery, participant responses, & program differentiation).</p>	<p>Interdisciplinary staff (RN, OT, PT). IRF- Neurovascular unit, New York</p>	<p>Tracking of Fidelity weekly.</p> <p>Continuous education rate</p>	<p>Increased rate of fidelity because of educational intervention.</p> <p>Discovered that for continuity in rate of fidelity there must be continuous education of staff.</p>	<p>For successful implementation of EBG required continuous staff re-education.</p> <p>Limitation: It is time consuming to monitor fidelity.</p>

<p>To determine patients and nurses perceptions of continence bundle. (Brady et al., 2016)</p>	<p>Qualitative Study Semi-structured interviews of staff post intervention & patients after discharge. Key Variables: Severity of UI, perceptions, communication, knowledge, attitude, containment, continence rehab, staff training.</p>	<p>15 Stroke Survivors. 23 staff (14 RN & 9 NA) IRF-Scotland.</p>	<p>% of patient perception via four emerged themes. Rate of change in staff based on 6 questions.</p>	<p>Severity of UI influenced patient perceptions. Poor coordination of care with patient by nurses. Bad judgment of nurses equating continence merit on mobility level, neglecting right assessment of UI. education of staff on UI had a greater outcome than the usual care Shift of staff perspective from containment to promotion of continence was useful. UI bundle (EGB and staff empowerment) increases promotion of continence among stroke survivors.</p>	<p>Continence care should be flexible enough to accommodate recent developments and staff training for UI resolution. Limitations: Aphasic and cognitively impaired stroke survivors were excluded. Small sample size.</p>
<p>To investigate staff knowledge, perception, & management of UI. (Mathis et al., 2013)</p>	<p>A quasi-experiment with longitudinal design (pre & post). Survey- 38 questionnaires.</p>	<p>Convenience sample 166 employees (Nursing and non-staff) from 6 Nursing Homes. Midwestern, USA</p>	<p>Paired surveyed. %Change of knowledge of UI. Change in treatment & outcome.</p>	<p>Significant 53% increase in ability of staff to distinguish btw UI types. 65% improvement in identifying UI types symptoms.</p>	<p>Education on UI should be included in staff orientation and periodically in service.</p>

	A 6 week educational intervention		Combination of education strategies	<p>After the intervention, 97% of the participants embraced that UI is not normal than. Lack of education makes nurses to embrace the notion that UI is normal.</p> <p>Combination of class, online, cue and algorithm found to be effective in delivering practice change behavior</p> <p>79% of the staff have more than 3 years' experience.</p> <p>CNA (NA) involved more with direct care; more education should be given to this group.</p>	Limitations: Convenience & small sample size, & no control group.
To investigate adherence of nurses to ICONS (Identifying Continence OptioNs after Stroke) for UI post stroke. (Chesworth et al., 2015)	<p>Exploratory study (Phase 1 & 2).</p> <p>Clinical logs of interventions.</p> <p>Fidelity</p> <p>14-day period</p>	<p>Stratified sampling. Nurses. 289 participants from 8 IRFs in England & Wales.</p>	<p>% of clinical logs</p> <p>How timely the SVP/Time voiding</p> <p>Rate of adherence to SVP</p>	<p>Phase 1 not attainable due to 30 min window that not reliable.</p> <p>30 mins window made fidelity assessment a failure.</p> <p>Lack of gap & inconsistency in documentation.</p>	<p>Despite the hurdles of measuring adherence to protocols, its significant matter.</p> <p>Flexibility of fidelity of treatment must be included during measurement.</p> <p>Limitations: Reality is different from theoretical perspective.</p>

Phase 2. Gap btw actual & proposed voiding.	Grouping of data together undermined individual responses.
Revised method did not capture data needed.	
Improvement in adherence. Documentation was still a challenge (bias).	

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